

IONIC CONDUCTIVITY AND YOUNG'S MODULUS OF SOLID POLYMER ELECTROLYTES FOR SUPERCAPACITOR

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ABSTRACT

Solid polymer electrolytes (SPEs) are one of the most promising materials to be used in the structural composite electrolyte bearing high mechanical properties without sacrificing the ionic conductivity simultaneously. In this study, the SPEs using the epoxy and ionic liquid electrolyte (IL) have successfully been fabricated with an aim to serve in a multifunctional solid polymer electrolyte. SPEs were induced phase separation following two phase. One is epoxy resin, their hardener and catalyst, act as a scaffold of SPEs. Another is IL phase which lithium salt (Li TFSI) was dissolved to serve the ion conduction. We also introduced the nano filler to promote the properties of SPEs. As a result, Young's modulus was reached 1 GPa without decrease of ionic conductivity (2.9×10^{-4} S/cm).

1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, in portable electronic devices and hybrid vehicle industries there is a high demand for better energy storage systems such as capacitor or batteries. These renewable energy sources enable to reduce the carbon emissions and to increase the fuel efficiency. Among the various energy storage devices, supercapacitors have attracted a lot of attention thanks to their extraordinary power performance (charge/discharge), much longer cycle-life compared to other energy storage systems.

Though polymer electrolytes are widely applied for supercapacitors with their flexibility and processability they exhibit an inverse relation between ionic conductivity and Young's modulus. As a result, solid polymer electrolytes (SPEs) are of great interest as solutions to overcome the key issues of polymer electrolyte, owing to their multifunctional properties such as mechanically rigid and electrochemical stable characteristic.

Epoxy based solid polymer electrolyte was suggested by Matsumoto et al. It is one of the most promising SPEs for supercapacitors. Epoxy becomes matrix polymer of SPEs thanks to well crosslinked tree dimensional network, excellent thermal stability and high mechanical properties approximately 3 GPa. And ionic liquid electrolyte which lithium salt (Li TFSI) is dissolved used to make the ion conduction phase in the SPEs thanks to high ionic conductivity, good flame retardant as well as wide potential window.

However, these solid polymer electrolytes are not enough to overcome the trade-off relation. Al_2O_3 inorganic filler are added into the epoxy-based electrolytes with various contents to improve the multifunctional properties of SPEs. Al_2O_3 has the excellent dielectric properties and high strength and stiffness therefore it becomes the material of choice for solid polymer electrolyte applications.

In this study, epoxy was used as the matrix and ionic liquid electrolyte (IL) dissolved Li TFSI were used to maximize the ionic conductivity and mechanical properties of SPEs. The most promising concentration of epoxy and IL was selected to achieve high mechanical performance without the requisite ionic conductivity. And then, extensive efforts have been made on adding various concentrations of inorganic Al_2O_3 fillers directly into the blending solution consist with epoxy resin and ILE. As a result, this strategy allows simultaneously enhancing the ionic conductivity and Young's modulus, which provides insights for the design of multifunctional electrolytes for energy storage devices.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

As shown Fig. 1 these SPEs were fabricated with epoxy resin based on bisphenol A type DEGBA and its conventional hardening agent, methyl tetrahydrophthalic anhydride (MeTHPA), were purchased from KUKDO Chemical and SHIN-A T&C, Korea. N, N-Dimethylbenzylamine (BDMA), which used as catalyst for the formation of epoxy resins. And bis(trifluoromethane)- sulfonimide lithium salt (Li TFSI), 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide- (BMIM-TFSI) and Al₂O₃ inorganic filler (2-6 nm*200-400 nm) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich, Korea.

Figure 1: Chemical structure of epoxy resin, curing agent, catalyst, ionic liquid, and LiTFSI salt.

2.2 Fabrication of solid polymer electrolyte

The first steps of SPEs preparation procedure are 1 mol LiTFSI completely dissolved in BMIM-TFSI to make IL solution. The resulting solution was added to the epoxy resin (DEGBA), hardening agent (MeTHPA) and catalyst (BDMA) as stoichiometric proportions (100: 90: 1.5, respectively). The stirring of the mixture containing all components were continued several hours until a homogeneous mixture was formed. This mixed solution was cured in rectangular shape and between two different sizes of brass electrodes which likes sandwich, under certain condition. The 3 steps curing cycles are as following; 2h at 80 °C following by 1 h at 120 °C and 2h at 150 °C.

2.2 Fabrication of supercapacitor

The carbon slurry for conventional carbon electrodes for supercapacitor process is prepared, PVDF as a binder was dissolved in a NMP solvent was then added to the activated carbon (ACs) and conductive carbons (CCs) as the mass ratio of 8:1:1. The Activated carbons are the mostly used materials due to their large surface area (2000m²/g) and moderate cost. However, the large surface of ACs is associated with large porosity which reduces the electrical conductivity of the ACs network. Therefore conductive carbons were added into the carbon slurry to formation of the electrical conductive network. The materials were mixed until to form uniformed slurry. After etching aluminium foil substrate, slurry was coated onto the substrate which used a current collector using a film applicator. The carbon slurry coated electrode was dried at 60 °C and then in a vacuum oven at 120 °C for 3 hr to remove remaining solvents in the micro-pore of carbon materials.

A supercapacitor was fabricated by sandwiching SPEs between a pair of the carbon electrodes. The epoxy-based polymer electrolytes simultaneously served as electrolyte and separator.

2.2 Characterization

Thermal properties measurements were determined using a TA Instruments Q2000 differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) using 10 °C per min heating and cooling rates under inert argon gas atmosphere to measure possible phase transition in solid polymer electrolyte. Samples were hermetically sealed in aluminium pan. The first heating scan was conducted at a ramp rate of 10 °C per min from room temperature to 100 °C to remove adsorbed water and the second scan were performed from -90 °C to 120 °C to determine glass transition temperature (T_g). The T_g was taken as the inflection point in the DSC thermogram from the second heating scan.

Prior to SEM analysis, each sample was placed in ethanol during 2 days and subsequently dried in an oven at room temperature under reduced pressure to evaporate the ethanol. SEM images of the extracted sample were recorded on a JEOL, JSM-5800 scanning electron microscope (SEM) with an accelerating voltage of 10 kV, after gold sputter coating for 120 s.

The ionic conductivity of the SPEs was measured by dielectric relaxation spectroscopy (DRS) using a Novocontrol GmbH Concept 40 broadband dielectric spectrometer. The dielectric permittivity was measured using a sinusoidal voltage input with 0.1 V amplitude and $10^{-1} - 10^7$ Hz frequency range and stepwise 5 K temperature changes for all experiments. Samples were covered two different size brass electrode, top and bottom electrodes. After curing, sandwiched solid polymer electrolyte was placed on top to create a parallel plate capacitor cell and loaded into a cryo-furnace with nitrogen atmosphere. Each sample was annealed in the instrument at 120 °C to remove any moisture. Data were collected in isothermal frequency sweeps from 120 °C to -100 °C.

The mechanical properties of samples were tested using a Q 800 from TA Instrument. Rectangular shape samples are tested to estimate the Young's modulus of SPEs.

Electrochemical stability and cell performance were evaluated by cyclic voltammetry (C-V) and galvanostatic charge-discharge (GCD) experiments. The electrochemical analysis was performed using a VSP300 from Bio-Logic Science Instrument. Potentiostat was measured in the potential range of 0 to 2.5 V to examine the influence of the potential sweep rate. The C-V was measured at a sweep rate of 10, 20, 50 and 100 mV/s. To test the charge/discharge performance, the cell using SPEs was charged and discharged with the potential range 0 to 2.5 V at the constant current 0.13, 0.20, 0.33, 0.50, 0.66 A/g.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The SPEs were investigated by combining epoxy resin, ionic liquids and Al_2O_3 filler. Their ionic conductivities and Young's modulus are dependent on the contents of ionic liquids. As the contents of ionic liquid electrolyte increase, the ionic conductivity is also increased up to 6.8×10^{-4} S/cm as shown in Fig. 2 (a). On the other hand, it leads to decrease Young's modulus compared to the modulus of an intrinsic resin. As noted in the introduction, both vital properties have a trade-off relation. Its Young's modulus (550 MPa) is unsatisfactory to meet the safety requirements of electric vehicles and portable devices, although 50 ILE (50 wt% ionic liquid content) has a high ionic conductivity (2.6×10^{-4} S/cm). We selected the 50 ILE as the most promising concentration to investigate the effect of filler in SPE based on simultaneously high ionic conductivity and Young's modulus compared to 30 and 70 ILEs as shown in Fig. 2 (b).

Figure 2: (a) Temperature dependence of ionic conductivity for solid polymer electrolytes containing different concentration of IL and (b) Ionic conductivity and Young's modulus of solid polymer electrolyte containing different concentration of IL.

Generally, the ionic conductivity of solid polymer electrolyte is defined as follows equations (1).

$$\sigma = n \cdot e \cdot \mu \quad (1)$$

where n , e and μ refer to the number of charge carriers, the ionic charge and the ionic mobility,

respectively. Ionic conductivity is noticeably improved from ~ 0 (0 ILE) to $\sim 2.6 \times 10^{-4}$ S/cm (70 ILE) due to the fact that the number of carrier ions and their mobility are increased by increase the IL contents as shown in Fig. 2 (a). And the relationship between ionic conductivity and temperature for the solid polymer electrolyte follow the Arrhenius forms for the conductivity as follow equations (2).

$$\sigma_{\text{DC}}(T) = AT^{-1/2} \exp\left[-\frac{E_a}{R(T-T_0)}\right] \quad (2)$$

wherein A is the pre-exponential constant at infinite temperature, the number of charge carriers, E_a is equivalent to the activation energy for ion conduction, R is the gas constant, and T_0 is the Vogel temperature.

To overcome this limitation, we decided to add inorganic fillers into the SPEs. The effect of Al_2O_3 was investigated using 50 ILE with various nanowires filler contents. In Fig. 3 (a), 50 ILE + 15wt% Al_2O_3 displays the highest conductivity (3×10^{-4} S/cm) and Young's modulus (1 GPa) at room temperature, which is higher than those without inorganic fillers. However, Al_2O_3 contents increases more than 15wt%, ion conductivity and Young's modulus decreases rapidly up to 1.7×10^{-4} S/cm and 670 MPa at the same time. The reason why the ion conductivity is not increased noticeably relative to the other polymer electrolyte containing Al_2O_3 filler is that the epoxy matrix is similar to semi-solid like materials. Therefore, the addition of the filler to the polymer is thought to be less on crystallinity effects.

Figure 3: (a) Temperature dependence of ionic conductivity for solid polymer electrolytes containing different concentration of Al_2O_3 and (b) Ionic conductivity and Young's modulus of epoxy-based solid polymer electrolyte containing different concentration of Al_2O_3 .

The epoxy matrix acting as internal framework is well cross-linked to establish a porous structure. IL is generally trapped into the porous structure and highly dispersed in the polymer matrix. Since the Young's modulus significantly drops from ~ 3 GPa (0 ILE) to ~ 40 MPa (70 ILE). In case of 30 ILE, most of nano size pores are dispersed on the surface of polymer matrix. Therefore, it is difficult to diffuse the ions through the porous structure as shown in Fig. 4 (a). On the other hand, SPEs containing 50 and 70 ILE have the micro pore size and nano size pores (50 ILE, 200nm and 70 ILE, 1um). These pores are generated to the channels as ion path inside of the epoxy matrix as shown in Fig. 4 (b)-(c). Although Young's modulus significantly decreased as shown in Fig. 2 (b), ions are able to diffuse through the pore and the ionic mobility is also enhanced as the increasing pore size. These results reflect that these epoxy-based solid polymer electrolytes have an inverse correlation between ionic conductivity and Young's modulus.

According to the FE-SEM analysis of SPEs with different ratio of Al_2O_3 , it is clear to see interconnected domain of epoxy matrix become thicker than before. When the Al_2O_3 nano filler are separated completely and evenly within the epoxy matrix, the extent of Al_2O_3 /epoxy interaction is maximized. This results in the greatest enhancement of Young's modulus. Especially, the Al_2O_3 inorganic fillers are uniformly disperse in epoxy network without aggregation of Al_2O_3 until 15wt%

filler loading, which significantly contributes to the improved mechanical toughness. However, as more Al_2O_3 is added, the aggregates of fillers are observed, which might disturb the ion transport and increase of the interface resistance between the SPEs and brass electrodes. In the Fig. 4 (d)-(e), the epoxy matrix of SPEs with over the Al_2O_3 15 wt% is not act as a reinforced scaffold anymore. It is because that a difficulty of Al_2O_3 dispersion. Thus, both ionic conductivities and Young's modulus of electrolytes are considerably diminished at the same time as shown in Fig. 3 (b).

Figure 4: FE-SEM image of SPEs with different concentration of (a)-(c) 30 ILE, 50 ILE and 70 ILE (d)-(e) 50 ILE+15 and 25wt% Al_2O_3 , (f) FE-SEM EDS spectrum of 50 ILE+15 wt% " Al_2O_3 ".

Fig. 5 (a) shows the assembled supercapacitor device, which wrapped in a pouch cell. We can turn on a red light-emitting diode (LED) in order to demonstrate the applicability of supercapacitor using SPEs as the actual device. The electrochemical performance of the supercapacitor using SPEs was compared based on cyclic voltammetry (C-V) and galvanostatic charge–discharge (GCD) analysis. The C-V curve is deformed rectangular shape for an electrical double layer capacitor (EDLC).

Figure 5: (a) Cyclic voltammetry(C-V) profiles at different scan rates from 10 to 100 mV/s. and (b) Galvanostatic charge/discharge (GCD) profiles at various currents from 20 to 170 mA

As shown in Fig. 5 (a), fabricated supercapacitor has the typical electrical double layer capacitor characteristic. And C-V curves exhibit near ideal capacitive behavior with a rectangular shaped curve at lower scan rates. On the other hand, increasing scan rates distort the ideal C-V curve. It is because the electrochemical kinetics can't respond to the rapid change in potential at extreme scan rates. As a result, good kinetic reversibility is the one of the most important factors for ideal capacitor characteristic. The GCD technique applies a constant current density and measures the responsive potential with respect to time. The GCD profile, with its triangular symmetrical distribution, also indicates good capacitive properties for EDLC. In addition to C-V, GCD is an alternative method to measure the capacitance of the solid polymer electrolyte. The GCD technique applies a constant

current density (e.g., A/g) and measures the responsive potential with respect to time. Generally, the working electrode is charged to a preset potential and the discharge process is then monitored to assess the capacitance. The specific capacitance of the supercapacitor using the SPEs as separator can be calculated according to the equation (3)

$$C = (I \cdot \Delta t) / (m \cdot \Delta V) \quad (3)$$

The electrochemical measurements of a supercapacitor using epoxy-based solid polymer electrolyte are conducted in the symmetric cell at room temperature. Fig. 2 (a) presents the result of C- V curves in the voltage window from 0 to 2.5V. The capacitance of the supercapacitor is evaluated by GCD measurements at different current densities as shown in Fig. 2 (b). The high specific capacitance of 90 F/g is obtained using the supercapacitor at a current density of 0.13 A/g.

4 CONCLUSION

The objective of this study was to develop SPE that optimize simultaneous ionic conductivity and mechanical properties. We successfully fabricated the epoxy-based solid polymer electrolytes. Their ionic conductivity and Young's modulus strongly depend on the contents of the ionic liquids. Ionic conductivity was enhanced with an increase of ionic liquid electrolyte concentration and the 70 ILE exhibits the highest conductivity (6.8×10^{-4} S/cm, 25 °C) among electrolytes under investigation. On the other hands, Young's modulus was decreased with an increase of ILE weight fraction in SPE. To overcoming the trade-off relationship, inorganic filler was added into the SPE. As a result, Young's modulus were promoted (1 GPa) without decrease of ionic conductivity (2.9×10^{-4} S/cm). Ionic conductivity and mechanical properties of electrolytes depends on the contents of Al₂O₃ filler. By adding different contents of inorganic Al₂O₃ filler, the morphology of SPEs, interconnected epoxy scaffold, is more ticker than before. Through the enhancement of Young's modulus, the limited properties of SPE are improved.

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